

ESL FOR STUDENTS WITH SPEECH AND LANGUAGE DISORDERS

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Abstract: ESL education for students with speech and language disorders is one of the important areas aimed at alleviating the difficulties they encounter in the process of language learning and ensuring effective learning. Speech and language disorders can manifest themselves in various forms, for example, difficulties in pronunciation, slowness in speech, grammatical errors, limited vocabulary, or problems in speaking and listening. Such disorders complicate language learning for students, therefore, it is necessary to develop special approaches and teaching methodologies for them.

Keywords: speech, language, English, grammatical errors, speaking, cooperation, pronunciation, lesson, context.

1.INTRODUCTION

ESL education requires an individual approach for students with speech and language disorders. Each student's speech deficiencies and learning needs can be different. For this reason, teachers must develop tailored curricula for each student, stay in close contact with students and constantly monitor their progress. Working in collaboration with speech therapists, on the other hand, is of great help in eliminating language and speech disorders. Exercises aimed at improving pronunciation are very important for students with speech disorders. These exercises train students to produce sounds correctly, increase accuracy in speaking, and help reduce speech errors. Pronunciation exercises are often conducted individually, since each student's problems are specific. It will also be useful to use various audio and video materials to improve pronunciation.

2.MATERIALS AND METHODS

Increasing vocabulary is also one of the important tasks for students with speech and language disorders. The extensive use of visual aids, painting, and graphics in teaching new words in ESL classes makes learning easier for students. The emphasis on the use of words in context, encouraging their use in everyday life situations, makes language learning effective. Games, interactive exercises, and group activities are also used to increase vocabulary. And when teaching grammar, simple and understandable comments, many examples and practical exercises are important. It is often difficult for students with speech and language disorders to learn grammatical rules, so teachers need to approach them patiently and explain each topic step by step. The use of more communication-based techniques in the study of rules will be more effective for students. To develop language comprehension and listening skills, ESL courses offer exercises based on various audio materials, stories, dialogues and real-life situations. For students with speech and language disorders, strengthening listening skills increases their confidence in communication and helps them better understand the language. Listening exercises also have a positive effect on improving student speech.[1]

3.RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Communication-based teaching techniques are particularly important for students with speech and language disorders. These techniques teach students to actively speak, freely

express their thoughts and participate in conversation. Group work, role-playing games, conversation exercises also develop social skills among students, which makes their learning process more interesting and effective. The use of technology in ESL education is of great help for students with speech and language disorders. With the help of special programs, mobile applications, online platforms, students can practice independently. This makes it possible to make learning permanent, to eliminate speech deficits more quickly. Also, interactive technologies increase motivation and make the learning process more interesting. It is also important for students to provide constant support and mental support. Speech and language disorders often lead to decreased self-confidence, which complicates the learning process. Teachers, parents and professionals should encourage students, appreciate their success, and also positively assess any small achievement. This increases motivation for students and encourages them to learn more actively.[2]

For students with speech and language disorders, it is necessary to establish a system of continuous monitoring and evaluation in ESL education. With the help of an assessment, student development is observed, in which areas there are difficulties, and the educational process is adapted. This system serves as a guiding tool for students and helps them develop their self-assessment skills. For students with speech and language disorders, professional training of teachers is of great importance in improving the effectiveness of ESL education. Teachers should have sufficient knowledge of speech disorders, be able to apply modern methods and technologies, and be in close contact with students. At the same time, working in collaboration with speech therapists, psychologists and other specialists increases the quality of Education.[3]

4.CONCLUSION

In summary, ESL education for students with speech and language disorders requires specific approaches and techniques to make their language learning process effective. Exercises aimed at increasing Individual planning, pronunciation and vocabulary, communication-based training, technology use, continuous support and evaluation system are the main components of this process. All this will help students improve their language skills, increase their self-confidence and become more active in social life. As a result, students with speech and language disorders not only learn the language perfectly through ESL education, but also succeed in their personal and academic development.

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